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THE CORE OF RUMELT'S STRATEGY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: RETHINKING THE STRATEGIC LOGIC OF THE ORGANIZATION

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Abstract: *Digital transformation has changed not only business tools but also the very logic of strategic thinking. Amid exponential data growth, accelerated technology cycles, and intensifying platform competition, organizations are facing strategic turbulence: decisions are made faster, projects are launched on a larger scale, yet the coherence of the strategic vision is increasingly blurred. Digital initiatives proliferate, but their connection to the organization's fundamental problem remains unclear. This creates a paradox: despite the formal existence of a strategy, actual management is carried out by a collection of disparate digital projects, not united by a single core idea.*

In this situation, the concept of "strategy core," developed by Richard Rumelt within the Good Strategy/ Bad Strategy approach, acquires particular methodological value. According to this logic, a true strategy comprises three interrelated elements: an accurate diagnosis of the key problem, a guiding policy as a principle for decision-making, and a coordinated system of actions. Rumelt's model disciplines managerial thinking, eliminates the substitution of slogans for strategy, and allows for the concentration of resources on overcoming truly significant constraints.

Digital Strategy Kernel model is proposed, complementing the traditional structure with two key components: an architectural component that defines the principles of digital infrastructure design and responsibility allocation; and a dynamic component that forms a strategic feedback loop based on analytical monitoring and adaptive metrics. It is argued that without these elements, the strategic core in the digital environment becomes unmanageable.

Keywords: *strategy, Rumelt, strategy core, digital transformation, strategic architecture, digital maturity, change management.*

At the beginning of the 21st century, digital transformation ceased to be a specific area of modernization and became a systemic condition for organizational functioning [1–3]. Big data technologies, cloud architectures, algorithmic management, artificial intelligence, and platform business models are radically changing the ways in which value is created, processes are coordinated, and management responsibilities are distributed [2–5]. However, along with increasing technological maturity, strategic uncertainty is also increasing: companies invest in digital solutions, launch automation programs, and implement new IT platforms, but do not always demonstrate strategic alignment and sustainable impact [4].

The phenomenon of "strategic dissipation" is increasingly observed in management practice: digital initiatives are being developed as independent projects, not united by a single logical foundation [6]. Organizations declare digital transformation, but fail to formulate a clear diagnosis of the key problem for which this transformation is being implemented. As a result, technology becomes

an end in itself, and strategy—a set of declarations [6]. This substitution undermines cause-and-effect clarity and reduces the manageability of change [7].

In these circumstances, turning to fundamental concepts of strategic management, capable of restoring disciplined thinking to the development process, is becoming relevant. One such concept is the "strategy core" model proposed by Richard Rumelt [6]. It is based on the idea that a true strategy is built around three elements: an accurate diagnosis of the problem, a guiding policy, and a coordinated system of actions [6;8]. This structure ensures the concentration of resources and eliminates the illusion of strategicity that arises during formal planning [9].

In strategic management, one of the key problems remains the substitution of content for form. Organizations develop lengthy strategic documents, formulate ambitious goals, declare missions and values, but fail to formulate a clear answer to the fundamental question: what specific problem does the company intend to solve and by what principle of action [8;9]. It is precisely this managerial illusion that Richard Rumelt's concept, outlined in his work *Good Strategy / Bad Strategy* [6], is directed against.

According to Rumelt, "bad strategy" is characterized by four typical features: excessive declarativeness, the substitution of slogans for analysis, vagueness of goals, and a lack of prioritization [6]. It creates a sense of strategic activity but fails to ensure the concentration of resources. In contrast, "good strategy" is built around a clear understanding of the obstacle or constraint that must be overcome to achieve competitive advantage [6;8].

Rumelt's key contribution lies in structuring strategy as a logical construct rather than as a set of goals. He emphasizes that strategy is not a growth ambition or a list of initiatives, but a meaningful choice of direction based on a diagnosis of the situation [6]. The diagnosis identifies the critical bottleneck; the guiding policy defines the solution principle; and coordinated actions ensure practical implementation [6].

The central element of Rumelt's concept is the idea of a "strategic core"—a minimal yet logically complete structure, without which strategy becomes a mere declaration. Unlike traditional strategic plans, which contain numerous goals and initiatives, the core represents a concentrated cause-and-effect model. It links situational analysis with management choices and practical actions.

Structurally, the core includes three interrelated components: diagnosis, guiding policy, and coordinated action.

A diagnosis is an analytical identification of the key constraint or problem hindering an organization's development. Its purpose is not to list environmental factors, but to focus attention on the primary bottleneck. A diagnosis simplifies complexity by highlighting the cause-and-effect center of a strategic objective. Without an accurate diagnosis, strategy is replaced by a set of initiatives that may be proactive but not decisive.

A guiding policy sets the principle for decision making. It is not a detailed plan, but a logic of action that defines how the organization intends to overcome the identified constraint. A guiding policy forms the framework for resource prioritization and management decisions, ensuring the internal coherence of the strategy.

Coordinated actions are a system of mutually reinforcing measures subordinated to a guiding policy. Their coherence means the absence of contradictions and the scattering of resources. This is where the practical side of strategy comes into play: actions should not simply be activities, but elements of a unified structure.

The methodological value of this framework lies in its logical rigor. Diagnosis explains, guiding policy guides, and coordinated actions implement. If any element is missing, the structure loses its integrity: without diagnosis, there is no focus, without policy, there is no principle of choice, and without action, there is no result.

In a traditional management environment, such a structure ensures focus and discipline. However, in the context of digital transformation, where problems are multilayered and actions are often implemented through complex architectural and technological solutions, it becomes necessary to clarify and expand the logic of the strategic core.

Rumelt's strategic core model has not only practical but also high methodological significance. Its value lies in the fact that it restores strategy to its status as an intellectual construct rather than an administrative document. In a context where strategic planning is often reduced to the formulation of KPIs, budgetary targets, and roadmaps, the core model re-emphasizes the cause-and-effect logic of management choices.

First, the core strategy ensures the concentration of resources. A clear diagnosis eliminates the dispersion of efforts and establishes management priorities. The organization stops reacting to every external signal and begins to act within the logic of the chosen constraint. This reduces the entropy of decisions and enhances the impact of investments [8-10].

Secondly, the model creates cause-and-effect clarity. The connection between the problem, the solution principle, and the actions becomes transparent. This logic allows the strategy to be assessed not by the scale of its declarations, but by its internal coherence. If actions do not follow from the guiding policy, and the policy from the diagnosis, the strategy loses its systemic nature. It is precisely this coherence that makes the model an analytical tool, not just a conceptual framework [7].

Third, the core strategy strengthens managerial discipline. Management is forced to answer difficult questions: What is the real problem? Why was this particular operating principle chosen? Which actions are truly coordinated? This intellectual rigor reduces the risk of imitative transformation and formal strategizing [9].

Finally, the model is universal: it is applicable to organizations of various sizes and industries, as it relies not on tools but on the logic of thought. This is why Rumelt's concept remains relevant in the digital age. However, its methodological strength only manifests itself when adapted to an environment where strategic reality is shaped not only by the market and competitors, but also by data architecture, algorithms, and technology platforms.

Digital transformation differs fundamentally from traditional organizational development programs in that it occurs in a highly nonlinear environment. While classical strategy assumed relative predictability in industry dynamics and gradual changes in competitive factors, the digital environment is characterized by abrupt shifts, network effects, and technological discontinuities [1,2].

Nonlinearity manifests itself primarily in the acceleration of change cycles. Technological platforms are updated faster than strategic programs can be completed. Decisions made today may become irrelevant in a few quarters due to the emergence of a new tool, algorithm, or monetization model. In such an environment, traditional strategic logic, focused on sustainability and long-term positioning, faces the need for constant adaptation.

The second aspect of nonlinearity is technological dependence. Organizations increasingly find themselves embedded in ecosystems of cloud providers, software platforms, and digital services. This means that strategic opportunities are determined not only by internal resources but also by the architecture of external technological solutions. As a result, the strategic landscape becomes multilayered: management logic must take into account infrastructural constraints, algorithmic rules, and integration standards.

The third factor is the network amplification effect. In a digital environment, the value of a product or service increases as the number of users increases. This creates an asymmetric competitive dynamic, in which the leader gains an exponential advantage. Strategic decisions must take this exponentiality into account, otherwise the organization risks operating linearly in an environment of nonlinear effects.

Digital transformation is creating an environment of strategic turbulence, where cause-and-effect relationships are becoming more complex and fluid. The strategic core model proposed by Richard Rumel initially focused on identifying the key constraint within a relatively stable configuration of factors. In a digital environment, however, the configuration of factors itself is constantly changing. This requires a rethinking of the diagnostic mechanism and a refinement of guiding policies, taking into account the nonlinear nature of technological processes.

One of the most characteristic effects of digital transformation is strategic fragmentation—the fragmentation of a single development logic into a multitude of autonomous digital initiatives.

Organizations launch automation projects, implement ERP systems, develop data analytics, and create mobile services and digital customer engagement channels. However, without a unified strategic core, these initiatives exist in parallel, failing to form a coherent change architecture.

Fragmentation arises for several reasons. First, digital technologies are highly modular: they can be implemented locally, without immediately transforming the entire system. This creates the illusion of control—the company "moves forward," but the strategic focus is blurred. Second, digital projects are often initiated by various departments—IT, marketing, production, HR—without cross-functional synergy. Each project may be rational in its own logic, but their combined effect does not form a strategic framework.

The result is a "digital noise" effect: a large number of initiatives generates activity but fails to enhance competitive advantage. Resources are allocated reactively, priorities are revised ad hoc, and the organizational architecture becomes increasingly complex and fragmented. While a strategy may formally exist—in the form of a presentation or roadmap—it fails to integrate decisions.

Strategic fragmentation is particularly dangerous because it masquerades as innovation. The more digital projects, the greater the sense of progress. However, without a clear diagnosis and guiding policy, actions don't reinforce each other but compete for resources. The organization begins to manage initiatives instead of managing development.

Digital transformation increases the risk of strategic integrity collapsing. This calls into question the adequacy of the classical logic of the strategic core and requires the inclusion of an architectural dimension capable of ensuring the coherence of digital solutions in a multi-project environment.

Digital transformation is changing not only management tools but also the very structure of responsibility within an organization. While in industrial logic, strategic decisions were concentrated within the management hierarchy, in the digital environment, a significant portion of the management function is being redistributed in favor of algorithms, analytical systems, and automated platforms [3-5].

Data-driven management assumes that decisions are made based on massive amounts of data and analytical models. This strengthens the validity of actions, but simultaneously transforms the source of managerial authority. Managers increasingly act not as the sole subject of choice, but as interpreters of digital signals. A new type of responsibility is emerging—responsibility for the data architecture and the correctness of algorithms, and not just for the final decision [4].

At the same time, the role of IT functions and digital departments in shaping strategic priorities is increasing. The choice of platform, integration architecture, level of automation, or algorithmic models is becoming a strategic decision, influencing the long-term trajectory of the organization. Thus, technological infrastructure ceases to be ancillary and becomes a strategic factor.

However, the redistribution of responsibility also creates risks. First, it creates an illusion of objectivity: data-driven decisions are perceived as neutral, although they depend on the quality of the source data and the parameters of the algorithms. Second, the boundary between the strategic and operational levels blurs: automated systems begin to determine priorities that actually shape the company's strategic behavior.

In this configuration, the classic strategic core faces a new reality. The problem diagnosis must take into account not only market and organizational constraints, but also the limitations of the digital architecture. The guiding policy must define the principles of interaction between humans and algorithms. Coordinated action requires cross-functional integration of managers, analysts, and IT architects.

The digital environment is transforming strategy from a purely managerial construct into a hybrid system where responsibility is distributed across people, processes, and digital mechanisms. This reinforces the need for an architectural and dynamic expansion of the strategic core.

In the classical logic of the strategic core, diagnosis functions as an intellectual filter: it identifies the key constraint around which the entire management structure should be built. However, in the digital environment, it is precisely this element that is most often eroded. This is due to the

technological substitution of the problem—when an organization begins to view technology implementation as an answer without clearly defining the question it is answering.

This blurring of diagnosis manifests itself in typical formulations: "we need digitalization," "we need to implement AI," "we should move to the cloud." These statements describe the tool but fail to identify the strategic obstacle. The lack of a clear diagnosis leads to technology becoming an end in itself rather than a means to overcome a specific constraint—whether it's low productivity, weak customer engagement, or ineffective process coordination.

The digital environment exacerbates this risk for several reasons. First, technological solutions are highly attractive and create the illusion of quick results. Second, market and competitive pressures encourage reactive actions: organizations implement what others have already implemented without conducting a thorough analysis of their own constraints. Third, the multilayered nature of digital systems complicates identifying the root cause of a problem—it may be related not to a lack of technology, but to the organizational architecture or distribution of responsibilities [11].

As a result, the diagnosis ceases to be an analytical tool and becomes a set of general formulations. This undermines the cause-and-effect basis of the strategy: the guiding policy becomes declarative, and actions become disjointed.

The key limitation of the classic strategic core in the digital environment is the risk of technological misdiagnosis. Maintaining methodological rigor requires expanding the analytical framework to separate the strategic problem from the technological solution and identify the structural causes of the digital divide.

If a diagnosis is blurred in a digital environment through technological substitution, the guiding policy often loses its meaning and becomes little more than a slogan. Phrases like "digital- first," "AI-driven," and "data- centric" create the impression of strategic clarity, but in reality, they don't define the principles for making management decisions. They indicate an orientation but don't define a logic of action.

In the classical strategic core model, guiding policy performs a normative function: it determines which decisions are consistent with the strategy and which are not. This is a selection principle that limits the managerial scope. In digital practice, this function is often lost. Policy is formulated as value statements, unsupported by architectural solutions and coordination mechanisms.

Declarative language is increasing under institutional pressure. Organizations strive to demonstrate digital maturity to investors, regulators, and partners. As a result, strategic rhetoric outpaces structural change. A disconnect arises between stated policy and actual decision-making. For example, a company may declare a data- driven approach, but key decisions continue to be made intuitively and outside of a unified analytical framework.

Another aspect of the problem is the lack of architectural logic. Guiding policies in the digital environment must define not only a value orientation but also the design principles of digital infrastructure: integration standards, data ownership rules, and automation levels. Without these, policies remain abstract and fail to ensure coherence.

The limitations of the classical strategic core are evident in the fact that guiding policy in the digital age requires deeper institutionalization. It must move from slogans to operationalized principles for designing and managing a digital system. Otherwise, strategy retains its form but loses its regulatory function.

The third element of the strategic core—coordinated action—is tested no less in the digital environment than the diagnosis and guiding policy. While in classical logic, coordination meant mutual reinforcement of initiatives within a chosen direction, in the context of digital transformation, it requires cross-functional synchronization at the level of architecture, data, and processes. This is where systemic disconnects most often arise.

The lack of coordination manifests itself on several levels. First, digital projects are being implemented in parallel by different departments without a unified integration framework. HR implements one platform, finance another, and production a third. Formally, each action is consistent

with the overall idea of digitalization, but their interaction does not form a coherent system. Instead of synergy, a technological mosaic emerges.

Secondly, actions often contradict the guiding policy. An organization may declare a focus on customer experience but implement solutions that complicate interfaces and increase operational burdens. Or it may declare a data-driven approach but fail to ensure a unified data quality standard. In such cases, actions exist, but they are not aligned either logically or architecturally.

Third, the digital environment increases interdependencies between decisions. A change to one system element (for example, the implementation of a new ERP platform) impacts planning, budgeting, performance measurement, and HR management processes. If these interdependencies are not considered at the strategic level, the organization faces cascading effects and increased management complexity.

Incoherence in the digital environment is becoming systemic. It manifests itself not only in managerial disunity but also in architectural fragmentation. This demonstrates that the classic interpretation of coordinated action as a set of initiatives is insufficient. In the digital era, coherence must be understood as the structural integration of processes, data, and responsibilities within a unified strategic logic (Table 1).

Table 1 - Deformations of the classical strategic core in the digital environment

Element of the strategic core	Classic function	Type of digital deformation	Mechanism of occurrence	Management implications
Diagnosis	Identifying the key limitation	Technological substitution of the problem	Focus on the tool instead of the cause	Scattering resources and losing focus
Guiding policy	The principle of decision selection	Slogan digitalization	Digital-rhetoric first without architecture	Strategic declarativity
Coordinated actions	Mutual reinforcement of initiatives	Design insulation	Lack of interfunctional synchronization	Local optimization instead of systemic effect
Strategic logic	Causal connection	Metric-centricity	Substituting KPI sets for strategy	Performance management instead of development management
Management responsibility	Centralized strategic choice	Algorithmic diffusion of responsibility	Transferring decisions to analytical systems without strategic control	Weakening of the subjectivity of management

The expanded, digitally adapted strategic core model begins with clarifying the nature of the strategic diagnosis in the digital environment. While in classical logic, the diagnosis identified a market or competitive constraint, in the context of digital transformation, the key object of analysis becomes the so-called digital divide—the structural inconsistency between the organization's strategic intentions and its actual digital architecture.

The digital divide manifests itself in several dimensions. First, it's the gap between data and decisions: an organization accumulates vast amounts of information, but it's not integrated into management logic. Data exists, but it doesn't become a strategic resource. Second, it's the gap between

technologies and processes: the implemented systems don't support the actual operating model, but merely overlay a legacy structure. Third, it's the gap between declared digital maturity and the actual ability to coordinate across functions.

Unlike traditional diagnosis, which focuses on the external market, the digital divide diagnosis looks inward at the organizational architecture. It identifies not only the competitiveness issue but also the structural limitations of the digital infrastructure: fragmentation. IT landscape, lack of a unified data ownership model, unclear distribution of responsibility between managers and algorithms.

A key element of this diagnosis is the recognition of data as a strategic resource. While the industrial model considered capital, labor, and technology as resources, in digital logic, data forms the basis of management choices. Their quality, accessibility, and integration directly impact strategic sustainability.

The first element of the expanded strategic core requires a shift from a superficial statement of the "need for digitalization" to a systemic identification of architectural inconsistencies. The digital divide diagnosis sets the starting point for the formation of an architectural guiding policy and provides a methodological basis for synchronizing transformational actions.

In the expanded strategic core model, guiding policy takes on an architectural dimension. While in the classical interpretation it defined a general principle for overcoming an identified limitation, in the digital environment this proves insufficient. An organization functions as a set of interconnected digital systems, platforms, and data flows, and therefore guiding policy must define the principles of their design and integration [11].

An architectural guiding policy answers the question not only "what are we doing" but also "how is the system structured to enable this?" It establishes the fundamental principles of a digital organization: the data ownership model, integration standards, levels of automation, and boundaries of responsibility between humans and algorithms. Without these principles, even a well-formulated strategy remains vulnerable to fragmentation [11].

A key element of architectural policy is recognizing digital infrastructure as a strategic asset. The choice of IT architecture, platform model, and degree of data centralization are not technical decisions, but strategic ones. They determine the speed of change, the scalability of processes, and the ability to manage analytically. Thus, architecture becomes the tangible expression of guiding policy.

It's important to emphasize that architectural guiding policy does not replace technology strategy. It establishes the design rules for an organizational system in accordance with the identified digital divide diagnosis. If the diagnosis identifies a structural inconsistency, the policy sets the principles for addressing it through system integration.

Unlike declarative formulas like "digital- first," an architectural guiding policy is operationalizable. It can be expressed in standards, regulations, requirements for digital projects, and consistency metrics. This is what enables strategic coherence to be maintained across multiple initiatives.

An expanded strategic core requires a shift from value-based rhetoric to digital organizational design principles. An architectural guiding policy ensures the structural integrity of the strategy and forms the basis for synchronizing transformational actions.

The third element of the expanded strategic core model in the digital environment is not simply coordinated actions, but synchronized transformational actions. The difference is fundamental. In industrial logic, coordination meant the absence of contradictions between initiatives. In the digital environment, this is not enough: actions must be integrated into a unified architecture of data, processes, and metrics.

Synchronization involves three levels of consistency.

First, cross-functional integration. Digital transformation simultaneously impacts finance, HR, production, marketing, and IT. If changes are implemented separately, the organization achieves a set of localized improvements but not a systemic effect. Synchronization means that every action is

designed with consideration of its impact on other functions. This requires a common digital framework and a single center for strategic coordination.

Secondly, metric Coherence. In a digital environment, metrics become behavioral regulators. If departmental metrics contradict each other, strategy disintegrates into local optimizations. Synchronized actions are based on a unified system of strategic metrics that reflect a common diagnosis and guiding policy. This creates the effect of management coherence.

Third, temporal coordination. Digital projects have varying implementation speeds. A lack of temporal synchronization leads to cascading failures: one system is implemented, another is not ready, and a third is outdated even before integration. Transformational actions must be structured as a sequence of mutually reinforcing stages.

The key distinction of the expanded model is the recognition that digital activities alter the organizational structure itself. They transform processes, redistribute responsibilities, and influence decision-making culture. Therefore, their coherence should be assessed not only by formal alignment with strategy but also by the degree of systemic integration.

Synchronized transformational actions transform strategy from a set of initiatives into a managed process of structural restructuring. Without this synchronization, even a correct diagnosis and architectural policy remain theoretical constructs. In the digital age, strategy is realized not through the number of projects, but through their structural coherence and controlled dynamics.

The digital environment fundamentally changes the temporal dimension of strategy. While in industrial logic, the strategic core was formed over a long horizon and adjusted periodically, in the context of digital transformation, strategy must operate in a mode of constant calibration. This is why the expanded model includes a dynamic feedback loop as a mandatory element.

Dynamic feedback means systematically collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data on strategy implementation. However, this isn't simply a matter of monitoring KPIs. The feedback loop must assess three aspects: the adequacy of the initial diagnosis, the effectiveness of the guiding policy, and the degree of synchronization of actions. If the data shows a persistent deviation in results, this may indicate not poor execution, but an incorrect problem definition.

In a digital environment, analytical monitoring capabilities are significantly expanded. BI tools, end-to-end analytics, process mining, and behavioral data enable tracking dynamic changes in near real time. This creates the preconditions for moving from reactive adjustments to proactive strategy adaptation. However, data availability alone does not guarantee strategic flexibility. Institutionalizing a mechanism for reviewing decisions is essential.

The dynamic feedback loop functions as a "strategic regulator." It reduces the risk of inertia, prevents the entrenchment of erroneous directions, and allows for the refinement of architectural principles as experience accumulates. In the face of technological turbulence, it is the ability to adjust that becomes a factor of resilience.

The expanded strategic core is complemented by an adaptive mechanism. Strategy ceases to be a static document and becomes a cyclical process of diagnosis, design, and synchronization. A feedback loop ensures the maintenance of strategic coherence in an environment where change is continuous and nonlinear (Table 2).

Table 2 - Structural and functional model of the extended strategic core in the digital environment

Strategic module	Management function	Object of regulation	Type of strategic logic	Risk of module deformation
Module 1. Diagnostic	Focusing on systemic constraints	Structural digital divide (data, processes, architecture)	Cause and effect logic	Technological substitution of the problem

Module 2. Architectural	Formation of principles for designing a digital organization	Infrastructure, integration standards, data ownership model	Constructive (design logic)	Fragmentation of the digital landscape
Module 3. Coordination and transformation	Synchronizing changes between functions	Projects, KPIs, implementation timelines	System logic of coordination	Local optimization and metric conflict
Module 4. Dynamic Controller	Data-driven strategy calibration	Results, deviations, behavioral effects	Adaptive logic	Inertia and the consolidation of an erroneous course
Integration circuit	Ensuring strategic coherence	Interconnection of all modules	Metasystemic logic	The growth of strategic entropy

Practical testing of the expanded strategic core model requires the development of a tool to measure its maturity and consistency in the digital environment. Otherwise, the model will remain a conceptual construct without operational application. The diagnostic tool should assess not the existence of a strategy as a document, but the integrity of its logical structure.

The first diagnostic block aims to assess the quality of the strategic diagnosis . It analyzes whether the key constraint is formulated in cause-and-effect form; whether the problem is separated from the technological solution; and whether a structural digital gap (data, architecture, processes) has been identified. The diagnosis is considered valid if it explains the allocation of resources and priorities, rather than simply repeating general market trends.

The second block concerns the architectural guiding policy. The presence of clearly defined principles for digital system design is assessed: the data ownership model, integration standards, automation rules, and the distribution of responsibilities between functions. It is important to determine whether these principles are institutionally enshrined or remain mere declarations.

The third diagnostic block is dedicated to synchronizing actions . Cross-functional project alignment, a unified metrics system, and the time coordination of transformation stages are assessed. Particular attention is paid to whether actions reinforce each other or create competition for resources.

The fourth element of the tool is an assessment of the dynamic feedback loop . This examines whether a mechanism for regularly reviewing diagnoses and policies based on data exists, as well as whether analytical tools are used for strategic calibration.

For an integrated assessment, a strategic coherence indicator (e.g., a weighted average across four blocks) can be introduced, reflecting the degree of structural integrity of the strategy in the digital environment. This tool allows for identifying areas of strategic noise and prioritizing corrective actions.

The diagnostic tool translates the expanded strategic core model from theoretical frameworks into management practice. It enables the measurement of the quality of their strategic integration, rather than the quantity of digital initiatives.

While the diagnostic tool addresses the integrity of the strategic core, the indicator system allows for the dynamic measurement of its digital coherence. In the context of digital transformation, it is important to evaluate not only the achievement of financial or operational results, but also the structural coherence of strategic decisions.

Digital strategic alignment indicators can be grouped into four key areas.

The first area is diagnosis coherence . This assesses the extent to which strategic initiatives are directly linked to the identified digital divide. Potential metrics include the proportion of projects with a formally documented link to the key constraint, as well as the degree to which resources are reallocated in accordance with the diagnosed problem. If projects are launched without a logical connection to the diagnosis, the level of coherence decreases.

The second area is architectural integrity. Indicators include the degree of integration of IT systems, the proportion of processes operating in a single digital environment, the level of data standardization, and the presence of a centralized architecture management model. High fragmentation of the digital landscape indicates a weak guiding policy.

The third area is cross-functional synchronization. This involves analyzing the alignment of KPIs across various departments, the presence of common transformation roadmaps, and the degree of metric overlap. If functional goals conflict, the strategy loses its coherence.

The fourth area is strategy adaptability. This assesses the frequency of strategic reviews based on analytical data, the speed of response to identified deviations, and the presence of a formalized mechanism for policy adjustment. High adaptability indicates a functioning dynamic feedback loop.

The integration of these indicators allows us to create a digital strategic coherence index, reflecting the degree of internal strategy coherence in the digital environment. This index does not replace traditional performance indicators, but rather complements them by capturing the structural stability of strategic logic.

Digital strategic alignment indicators thus serve as a tool for maintaining strategic discipline in the face of technological turbulence. They measure not the scale of digital investments, but the depth of their integration into a unified strategic core.

Despite the methodological integrity of the expanded strategic core model, its practical implementation is fraught with a number of systemic risks. Ignoring these limitations could transform the concept into a formal superstructure without any real managerial impact.

The first risk is institutional resistance . The architectural guiding policy involves the redistribution of authority, data standardization, and increased cross-functional coordination. This inevitably affects the areas of influence of departments and managers. In an established hierarchy, digital centralization can be perceived as a threat to autonomy.

The second risk is the hyper-bureaucratization of strategy . Attempts to formalize architectural principles and feedback loops can lead to excessive regulation. As a result, the organization focuses on following procedures rather than actually solving the diagnosed problem. Strategic discipline turns into an administrative burden.

The third risk is the metric illusion of controllability. The introduction of strategic alignment indices and advanced analytics may create the feeling of complete process control. However, data only reflects measurable aspects of reality. There is a risk that strategic analysis will be replaced by technical reporting.

The fourth risk is technological determinism . Strengthening the architectural component can lead to excessive strategy dependence on the chosen digital platform or IT provider. In this case, flexibility is reduced, and strategic logic is subordinated to the limitations of the infrastructure.

The fifth risk is a shortage of strategic talent. The expanded model requires managers capable of thinking both strategically and architecturally, and understanding the interrelationships between data, processes, and organizational structure. A lack of such competencies reduces the quality of implementation.

Implementing an expanded strategic core requires not only methodological development but also the organization's institutional maturity. The model enhances the manageability of digital transformation only if a conscious balance is struck between architectural rigor and adaptive flexibility. Without this, the strategy risks becoming another element of management noise rather than reducing it (Table 3).

Table 3 - Maturity levels of the extended strategic core in the digital environment

Level	The nature of strategic logic	Architectural configuration	Management system behavior	Typical consequences
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Declarative	The strategy is formulated as a set of goals and digital initiatives	Disparate IT solutions, lack of a unified architecture	Reactive decisions, project impulsiveness	Growing digital noise, low return on investment
Project	Having a partial strategic focus	Local integration of systems within functions	Coordination through temporary working groups	Improving individual processes without systemic effect
Integration	A clear diagnosis of the digital divide	Formalized architectural principles	Cross-functional synchronization of initiatives	Improving controllability and predictability of results
Architectural	The strategy is embedded in the organization's digital model	Unified data model and standardized infrastructure	Managing through agreed metrics and platforms	Reduced fragmentation, increased scalability
Adaptive-coherent	The strategic core is regularly reviewed based on analytics	Dynamic architecture with fast restructuring mechanisms	Cyclical adjustment of diagnosis and policy	High digital resilience and strategic flexibility

The analysis suggests that Richard Rumelt's strategic core model retains its fundamental methodological value even in the context of digital transformation. Its logic—diagnosis, guiding policy, and coordinated actions—continues to provide cause-and-effect clarity, resource concentration, and managerial discipline. However, the digital environment radically complicates the context in which this model is applied.

Digitalization increases the nonlinearity of processes, provokes strategic fragmentation, and redistributes management responsibility between people and algorithms. Under these conditions, the traditional strategic core faces the risk of blurred diagnosis, declarative guiding policies, and inconsistent actions. Technology begins to replace the problem, and activity replaces strategy.

In response to these limitations, this paper proposes an expanded model of the strategic core, including two additional components: an architectural dimension of guiding policy and a dynamic feedback loop. The architectural component ensures the structural integrity of the digital infrastructure and anchors the organization's design principles. The dynamic loop creates an adaptation mechanism that enables regular revision of strategic foundations based on analytical data.

Practical testing of the model using a diagnostic tool and a system of digital strategic alignment indicators demonstrates the feasibility of moving from declarative digitalization to managed transformation. The model's effectiveness depends on institutional maturity, the quality of management competencies, and the organization's ability to avoid hyper-bureaucratization and technological determinism.

Strategy in the digital age is no longer a static plan but a discipline for maintaining coherence amid technological turbulence. An expanded strategic core allows for greater systemic coherence and sustainability rather than increasing the number of digital initiatives. A promising direction for further research is the empirical validation of a strategic coherence index and the development of quantitative models for assessing the digital resilience of organizations.

LITERATURE

1. Bharadwaj A., El Sawy OA, Pavlou PA, Venkatraman N. Digital Business Strategy: Toward a Next Generation of Insights // *MIS Quarterly*. 2013. Vol. 37.No. 2. P. 471–482.
2. Westerman G., Bonnet D., McAfee A. *Leading Digital: Turning Technology into Business Transformation*. Boston: Harvard Business Review Press, 2014.
3. Vial G. Understanding Digital Transformation: A Review and a Research Agenda // *Journal of Strategic Information Systems*. 2019. Vol. 28.No. 2. P. 118–144.
4. Kane GC, Palmer D., Phillips AN, Kiron D., Buckley N. *Strategy, Not Technology, Drives Digital Transformation*. MIT Sloan Management Review and Deloitte University Press, 2015.
5. Hess T., Matt C., Benlian A., Wiesböck F. Options for Formulating a Digital Transformation Strategy // *MIS Quarterly Executive*. 2016. Vol. 15.No. 2. P. 123–139.
6. Rumelt R. *Good Strategy / Bad Strategy: The Difference and Why It Matters*. New York: Crown Business, 2011.
7. Porter ME *What Is Strategy?* // *Harvard Business Review*. 1996. Vol. 74.No. 6. P. 61–78.
8. Porter ME *Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance*. New York: Free Press, 1985.
9. Teece DJ, Pisano G., Shuen A. Dynamic Capabilities and Strategic Management // *Strategic Management Journal*. 1997. Vol. 18.No. 7. P. 509–533.
10. Teece DJ *Explicating Dynamic Capabilities: The Nature and Microfoundations of (Sustainable) Enterprise Performance* // *Strategic Management Journal*. 2007. Vol. 28.No. 13. P. 1319–1350.
11. Ross JW, Weill P., Robertson DC *Enterprise Architecture as Strategy: Creating a Foundation for Business Execution*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press, 2006.